

English is all you need? Deep learning-based detection of fuzzy areas in radiographs made with a chatbot.

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Abstract:

In medical imaging, certain patterns must be repetitively detected on images obtained during the diagnostic process. Dental radiography is an example where lytic periapical areas, which reflect tooth morbidity, are ideal for proposing a system of shape detection.

The aim of the study was to evaluate whether a medical professional can successfully create and execute a U-Net for the aforementioned task. X-ray labeled and unlabeled images were presented. Python code was created with the help of ChatGPT, and the proposed code was executed in the Colab environment. The mean value of the loss function was 0.67, with a Mean Intersection over Union (IoU) value of 0.5 achieved during training, though accuracy was low. In the validation phase, the mean validation loss for the epochs was 0.64, the mean of the validation IoU was 1.0, but the mean validation accuracy remained low. These initial results are promising.

In conclusion, with the contemporary development of programming skills in chatbots, even individuals with no programming experience can create a network for training and validating results. The proposed approach may present a new direction for the medical community; however, the results obtained in this initial attempt are not yet applicable for any clinical tasks.

Keywords: artificial intelligence, pattern recognition, U-Net, medical images, ChatGPT, periapical lesions

1. Introduction:

Medical diagnosis using imaging relies on pattern recognition. This task in clinical medicine requires extensive training. However, deep learning networks, if trained with meticulously prepared ground truth and provided with large datasets, have been proven to yield stable, repetitive results [1,2]. When a patient suffers from dental pain, dental radiographs are the first and mandatory step of the diagnostic process [3]. If chronic inflammation of the dental pulp is present, periapical lytic lesions may form, indicating the status of the tooth to the dentist [4]. These informative lesions can be visualized on dental radiograms as periapical lytic areas, visible due to locally decreased bone density from ongoing metabolic

processes [5]. The resulting decreased calcium content makes the bone radiolucent, and the periapical lytic lesion appears as a “darker” fuzzy spot on the radiogram. Due to anatomical overlap of structures and small dimensions of lesions, the sensitivity of lesion detection by medical professionals is reported to be around 70% [6]. Therefore, attempts are made to analyze bone texture using radiogram features hidden from human visual perception [7,8]. There are also efforts to detect lesions using artificial intelligence methods. The use of CNN-U Net and combined architectures for lesion detection on panoramic and bitewing radiographs has resulted in mean sensitivity above 89% and mean specificity of 93%. Reported AI accuracy is high, reaching 90% in recent papers [9,10,11]. ChatGPT, with its code generation capabilities, may revolutionize medicine, but knowledge about doctors using this form of support is sparse [12]. The authors of this paper are medical doctors dedicated to using AI in their clinical work, and therefore, they use chatbots extensively. The current abilities of chatbots, especially the most broadly used ChatGPT by the medical community for programming various medical tasks, are not yet well explored. The authors undertook this task to evaluate whether it is possible to create a working U-Net architecture, train it with labeled radiograms (ground truth), and exploit results on validation data (on similar types of lesions) without any assistance or knowledge from technical professionals. The only conditions were the use of English language prompts and an infinite number of trials. The generated code had to be executed in Google Colaboratory.

The aim of the study is to evaluate whether a medical doctor with no knowledge of programming or external technical support is able to create, train, and validate a deep neural network architecture programmed by the most commonly used chatbot (ChatGPT) using only English language prompts.

2. Method:

2.1. Ethics Approval

The study protocol was designed in accordance with the guidelines of the Declaration of Helsinki and the Good Clinical Practice Declaration Statement. All images were carefully anonymized. Informed consent for the publication of anonymized medical images was obtained from the management of the dental clinic. Because the study was retrospective in nature and the radiograms were made during the routine diagnostic process, informed consent from patients was waived.

2.2 Chat prompting.

The following prompts were used in several iterations of the work. Examples are shown in their original form:

- “I want to create and use a deep net to find fuzzy shapes on radiograms. A training set with the marked region of interest is provided. Can you help me create the net and introduce the training set and data set, preferably in Colab, for further shape recognition? Examples are below.”

- “If I present to Colab ten input images and ten ground truth images with marked similar fuzzy areas on x-ray images and I present different images to make predictions on, can you help me create and train the net to accomplish this task with measurement of results? Sample images are provided in the attachment.”
- “How can I apply data augmentation if I have 10 input images, 10 ground truth images, and 10 images to exploit results on?”
- “At which step do I have to upload my training data where the net has to predict the location of fuzzy areas on images?”
- “I created a file 'zeby' on Google Drive where 'input', 'ground_Truth', and 'prediction' images are present.”
- “Can you propose code executable in Colab to present results on a scatter graph?”
- “Results should be verified on prediction images - the net should predict the presence of fuzzy areas on images.”
- “Can you propose the code for Colab to mark with an outline the predicted masks on the images?”

2.3. Environment Setup

The development environment for this project was set up using Google Colab, an online platform that provides free access to GPUs and TPUs, making it suitable for computationally intensive tasks like deep learning. Google Drive was used for storing the dataset, which includes input images, ground truth masks, and images for prediction.

The process began by mounting Google Drive in the Colab environment to facilitate seamless data access. Essential libraries for deep learning, data processing, and augmentation were imported, including TensorFlow for building the neural network, NumPy for numerical operations, Matplotlib for plotting, and Albumentations for data augmentation.

2.4. Data Preparation

Three sets of data were used: ten input images with no modifications, ten images with modifications presented as ground truth where fuzzy dark periapical areas indicating lytic regions were marked by black circles, and ten prediction images where lesions had to be marked.

The dataset was organized in a directory on Google Drive, with subdirectories for input images, ground truth masks, and prediction images. The directory structure was verified by listing the files to ensure the correct paths and filenames.

Input images and ground truth masks were then identified and their paths were sorted. This step ensured that each input image corresponded correctly with its ground truth mask.

Images and masks were loaded and preprocessed. This involved resizing all images to a standard size and normalizing their pixel values. The resizing ensured that the model could process the images efficiently, while normalization helped in faster convergence during training. The data was split into training and validation sets to enable model evaluation during training.

2.5. Data Augmentation

Data augmentation was applied to increase the diversity of the training dataset. Augmentation techniques such as horizontal and vertical flips, random rotations, transpositions, brightness and contrast adjustments, and random shifts and scales were used. This step was crucial for enhancing the model's ability to generalize from limited training data.

The augmented images and masks were combined with the original training data, resulting in a larger and more diverse dataset. This augmented dataset was then used for training the model.

2.6. Model Definition

A U-Net model architecture was defined for this task. The U-Net is a popular convolutional neural network architecture used for image segmentation tasks. It consists of an encoder (contracting path) and a decoder (expanding path) with skip connections that allow the network to use high-resolution features from the encoder in the corresponding decoder layers.

The encoder path captures the context of the input image, while the decoder path enabled precise localization. The skip connections helped in preserving spatial information that is often lost during down sampling in the encoder.

2.7. Model Training

The U-Net model was compiled using the Adam optimizer and binary cross-entropy loss function. The model was also configured to track accuracy and mean Intersection over Union (IoU) as metrics for performance evaluation.

The training process involved feeding the augmented training dataset into the model for a specified number of epochs. During training, the model's performance on the validation set was monitored to prevent overfitting. The training history, including accuracy and validation accuracy over epochs, was plotted to visualize the model's learning progress (Fig.3).

2.8. Model Evaluation

After training, the model was evaluated on the validation set to assess its performance. Key metrics such as validation loss, validation accuracy, and validation mean IoU were calculated. These metrics provided insights into the model's effectiveness in segmenting fuzzy areas in radiographs.

2.9. Prediction

The trained model was used to predict fuzzy areas on new images. The prediction process involved preprocessing a new image and passing it through the model to generate a predicted mask. The original image and the predicted mask were then visualized side by side to compare the results (Fig.1).

Fig 1. Presents Sample of images: Input image (original dental image with periapical lytic lesion) , Ground Truth with annotated lytic lesion by experienced radiologist lastly Prediction made on proposed images on validation set.

3. Results :

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4/4 [=====] - 37s 10s/step - loss: 0.6742 - accuracy: 3.8147e-06 - mean_io_u: 0.5000 - val_loss: 0.6504
Epoch 7/20
4/4 [=====] - 36s 9s/step - loss: 0.6733 - accuracy: 3.8147e-06 - mean_io_u: 0.5000 - val_loss: 0.6517
Epoch 8/20
4/4 [=====] - 36s 9s/step - loss: 0.6709 - accuracy: 3.8147e-06 - mean_io_u: 0.5000 - val_loss: 0.6473
Epoch 9/20
4/4 [=====] - 39s 10s/step - loss: 0.6679 - accuracy: 3.8147e-06 - mean_io_u: 0.5000 - val_loss: 0.6444
Epoch 10/20
4/4 [=====] - 37s 10s/step - loss: 0.6639 - accuracy: 3.8147e-06 - mean_io_u: 0.5000 - val_loss: 0.6301
Epoch 11/20
4/4 [=====] - 37s 9s/step - loss: 0.6692 - accuracy: 5.7220e-06 - mean_io_u: 0.5000 - val_loss: 0.6313
Epoch 12/20
4/4 [=====] - 36s 9s/step - loss: 0.6637 - accuracy: 5.7220e-06 - mean_io_u: 0.5000 - val_loss: 0.6319
Epoch 13/20
4/4 [=====] - 40s 10s/step - loss: 0.6615 - accuracy: 5.7220e-06 - mean_io_u: 0.5000 - val_loss: 0.6315
Epoch 14/20
4/4 [=====] - 36s 10s/step - loss: 0.6644 - accuracy: 5.7220e-06 - mean_io_u: 0.5000 - val_loss: 0.6361
Epoch 15/20
4/4 [=====] - 36s 9s/step - loss: 0.6651 - accuracy: 3.8147e-06 - mean_io_u: 0.5000 - val_loss: 0.6373
Epoch 16/20
4/4 [=====] - 36s 9s/step - loss: 0.6668 - accuracy: 3.8147e-06 - mean_io_u: 0.5000 - val_loss: 0.6351
Epoch 17/20
4/4 [=====] - 50s 14s/step - loss: 0.6613 - accuracy: 5.7220e-06 - mean_io_u: 0.5000 - val_loss: 0.6320
Epoch 18/20
4/4 [=====] - 36s 9s/step - loss: 0.6579 - accuracy: 5.7220e-06 - mean_io_u: 0.5000 - val_loss: 0.6337
Epoch 19/20
4/4 [=====] - 39s 10s/step - loss: 0.6603 - accuracy: 5.7220e-06 - mean_io_u: 0.5000 - val_loss: 0.6286
Epoch 20/20
4/4 [=====] - 37s 10s/step - loss: 0.6581 - accuracy: 3.8147e-06 - mean_io_u: 0.5000 - val_loss: 0.6300

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Figure 2. Presents training metrics - obtained in the process of model training evaluation in chosen epochs.

Training Metrics:

- The U-Net model was compiled and trained using the augmented dataset. The training process involved specifying the optimizer, loss function, and evaluation metrics.
- The mean value of the loss function was 0.67, which suggests that there is still a significant difference between the predicted and actual labels.
- The accuracy value was low, indicating a problem with the calculation method but also potentially with the definition of accuracy in this context.
- The Mean Intersection over Union (IoU) value of 0.5 indicates poor overlapping of the predicted masks on the true masks.

Validation Metrics:

- The mean validation loss for the epochs was 0.64, slightly lower than the training loss (0.67), which indicates that there might be room for improvement in learning the training data.
- The mean validation accuracy was 0.0000e+00, indicating very low accuracy and suggesting a need to revalidate (recalculate) the validation data.
- The mean of the validation IoU was 1.0, which suggests perfect overlap between the predicted masks and the true masks for the validation data.

Fig 3. The scatter plot represents the relationship between the original image pixel values and the predicted mask pixel values generated by the U-Net model, serving as a visualization of model performance. A positive correlation between the original image pixel values and the predicted mask values was observed. The spread in the predicted mask values for a given range of original pixel values indicates variability in the model's predictions. The spread and presence of outliers suggest that there is still room for improvement in the model's predictions.

Study Strengths:

- The visualization demonstrates that the creation and application of working code is temporarily possible for a person with basic user knowledge of applications but no programming skills. This is very promising for medical doctors, who are typically not educated in programming but are involved in many scientific and daily routine tasks with large datasets and pattern recognition.
- Despite using dental X-ray images with not well-defined borders, the results in this first attempt are promising, as the value of the loss function on the validation data was slightly lower than the training loss.

Study Weaknesses:

- The prompts' quality may be a little naïve, reflecting no special preparation for the task; however, this can be refined in future attempts.
- A small and limited dataset was used for this experiment.

- Metrics calculation was not verified to ensure that accuracy and mean IoU are being calculated correctly.
- Training data preprocessing was not verified to exclude incorrectly preprocessed data.
- Although the mean IoU in training suggests moderate performance, which can be interpreted as very good for an initial study, it is unsatisfactory as the proposed system does not produce correct labels and cannot be used in medical settings at this stage. This reflects, at least in part, the very limited dataset and uncontrolled process with no feedback.

Further study will include a larger dataset with well-controlled training and preprocessing processes to produce a stable, self-made environment for developing any medical shape recognition system.

4. Conclusion

The proposed methodology outlines a systematic approach to developing a deep learning model using the U-Net architecture for detecting shapes. As an example of this approach, the detection of fuzzy areas in radiographs was used. Basic user skills were implemented, utilizing Google Colab and Google Drive to make prepared data accessible. Data preparation, augmentation, training, and validation of the implemented U-Net were based on Python code proposed by ChatGPT. This work demonstrates the effectiveness of chatbots in creating workflows in the deep learning environment using prompts. However, while the proposed program is not yet applicable for operating on medical data, this approach indicates a promising direction for further development and should be supported with appropriate training.

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Author Contributions

Conceptualization, R.O. B.O.; Data curation, R.O. and B.O.; Formal analysis, R.O. Investigation, R.O. B.O. Methodology, R.O.; Project administration, R.O.; Resources, B.O.; Software, R.O.; Supervision, R.O.; Validation, R.O., B.O.; Writing—original draft, R.O.; Writing—review & editing, R.O and B.O.

Funding

This publication received no external funding.

Acknowledgments

They are no acknowledgments to declare.

Conflicts of Interest

The authors declare no conflict of interest.

